

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF MORAL AND AESTHETIC EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical and methodological foundations of moral-aesthetic education in the educational process. Also, educating young people to achieve aesthetic beauty and physical maturity by providing scientific understanding of the essence, goals and tasks of aesthetic education.

Key words: Aesthetic education, sophistication, artistic creativity, category, works of art, ethics, personal spirituality.

Introcudtion.

Every parent has a pedagogical instinct. Each of them brings up their children using different ways. In this regard, aesthetic education is one of the most effective ways. Aesthetic education is important both in the family, in the neighborhood, and among acquaintances. For this reason, showing the people of the country and people's attention as role models is an important ideological basis for increasing the effectiveness of education.

One of the main concepts of aesthetic education is the category of beauty. Explaining its meaning to students will also greatly help to ensure the viability of this education. Therefore, we found it appropriate to make the following approaches to revealing the essence of the concept of beauty:

- *beauty is the beauty of a person's heart;*
- *beauty is the warmth of a person's desire;*
- *beauty is the fact that a person has a beautiful character;*
- *beauty is a beautiful tree, its leaf is morality, its root is the inner world, and its fruit is good virtue.*

So, the beauty of a human child is humanity, which includes the best behavior and the best qualities of a person, in addition to the beauty given by nature.

Therefore, aesthetic education is both the education of sophistication and the education of humanity, and the education of beauty, which is of full importance. For this reason, education of students in an aesthetic spirit is a very complex, multifaceted dynamic process, with the help of which it is possible to obtain optimal options for carrying out the process of well-rounded personality education. "Aesthetic education - teaching students to perceive and correctly understand beauty in reality, in art, in nature, in people's social and labor relations, to develop their artistic taste, to instill love for beauty. is to cultivate the ability to shoot and bring beauty into one's life." "Aesthetic education and training is the formation of all kinds of views, situations, events and artistic-aesthetic thinking that arouse pleasure in a person and encourage him to action, courage and heroism."

"Aesthetic development is a long-term process consisting of the emergence and improvement of the aesthetic consciousness, attitudes and aesthetic activity of a person. This

process has different levels determined by social factors. It depends on the acquisition of the aesthetic culture of the society by the person, and it can be done in different ways. It is carried out with the help of forms and forms. It provides an understanding of the aesthetic culture of the society in various spiritual and material forms."

The content of aesthetic education of students is mainly:

- *existence of interest and need for aesthetics;*
 - *aesthetic knowledge;*
 - *formation of aesthetic skills and competencies;*
 - *perfection of aesthetic sense;*
 - *the presence of skills, emotions and abilities to enjoy one's own work and to evaluate the benefits;*
- *consists of a set of human qualities, such as the desire for beauty and the ability to cultivate tastes.*

The main goal of aesthetic education is to educate students and young people to feel beauty in a spiritual sense, to form a high aesthetic taste and love for works of art, to arouse respect for history and architectural monuments, to develop ideas about a conscious attitude to our beloved nature. It consists in educating human qualities such as developing skills and abilities to improve, to appreciate the wealth of nature and society.

Based on the main goal of aesthetic education, it can be noted that with its help, it is necessary to educate the young generation as a socially active person enjoying the best examples of the artistic culture of our country and the world.

Aesthetic education is aimed at improving the artistic and creative abilities of the young generation, that is, students. The tasks of aesthetic education will be to realize its main goal. Efforts to reform education in our independent republic should also be taken into account. It is better to carry out aesthetic education in higher educational institutions in the following directions, and each of these directions is one of the tasks in solving the main goal of aesthetic education: to determine the need for aesthetic education among students and young people. In this, their spiritual sense of beauty; presence of aesthetic consciousness and taste, aesthetic reasoning and interests; students like to improve their aesthetic taste; having respect for national and spiritual values; it is determined that the spouse has a sense of respect for the Motherland, parents and friends, and so on;

Aesthetic need refers to a set of specific aspects that urge a person to study and learn the world around us aesthetically, to a certain type or direction of his artistic activity.

- formation of the spiritual image of the scientific worldview.
- to determine the aesthetic inclination of students. These are determined by the presence of knowledge, skills and competence in students about positive qualities such as aesthetic excitement, aesthetic judgment, aesthetic attitude, artistic and aesthetic taste, aesthetic interest, aesthetic feeling, aesthetic perception and aesthetic assessment.
- to determine the formation of aesthetic consciousness. It is important to pay attention to the formation of thoughts, ideas, visions, theories and teachings as a result of artistic education and training, which are formed in the process of direct communication of aesthetic education with social reality, nature, art. The basis of aesthetic consciousness is aesthetic perception, which appears when a person encounters beauty and is characterized by its orientation to a specific goal. With the formation of aesthetic consciousness, it is possible to educate young students to correctly understand the essence of couples such as beauty and

ugliness, generosity and stinginess, kindness and rudeness, happiness and sadness, joy and sadness, salvation and disaster. . Through this, a correct conscious attitude towards the environment and an understanding of beauty is formed in the youth;

- formation of knowledge, skills and qualifications about the essence of the categories of aesthetic education in the minds of students. This includes aesthetic culture, cultural heritage, personal aesthetic culture, aesthetic consciousness, aesthetic perception, aesthetic debate, aesthetic ideal, aesthetic interest, aesthetic knowledge, aesthetic inclination, aesthetic taste, aesthetic feeling, aesthetic reasoning, aesthetic need, aesthetic attitudes. , is achieved by instilling knowledge, skills and competencies about the content of such categories as aesthetic activity;

In this, it is necessary to pay attention to learning about life, understanding sophistication, strengthening the whole image of a person, that is, his feelings and aesthetic will;

- organization of aesthetic education based on national and spiritual values. It is necessary to pay more attention to the spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people from the past. In particular, materials related to aesthetics in the life and work of encyclopedists, scholars of hadith, poets, writers, historians, statesmen, and national heroes create ample opportunities for conducting aesthetic education.

Morality is one of the forms of social consciousness, which expresses its essence, personal behavior, behavior, lifestyle, principles and rules of living, as well as the content of social relations. Therefore, morality as a social phenomenon has a unique importance in the spiritual and spiritual life of society. This concept serves as one of the main criteria in the process of determining the image of a particular nation and its place in personal development.

The concept of "ethics" was formed at the first stage of human society in the form of regulatory activity based on public opinion. Since ancient times, this concept has been used in various forms in socio-philosophical, psychological, pedagogical, historical, artistic, ethnographic and cultural works.

Morality (Arabic means behavior) is one of the forms of social consciousness, a social order, which serves to regulate people's behavior in all spheres of social life. Ethics differs from other forms of regulation of public activities (education, production, folk traditions) in that its requirements are justified, implemented, and regulated on the basis of public opinion. Moral requirements are in the form of a voluntary duty that applies to everyone, but is not carried out on the basis of any special command or instruction of anyone. Fulfillment of moral requirements occurs only within the framework of forms of moral influence.

Morality is the basis and foundation of spiritual perfection, which is the highest stage of personal development. In a word, morality is a set of behavioral norms accepted in society and approved by public opinion.

The organization of spiritual and moral education is considered the most important factor that ensures the success of social education. Spiritual-ethical education and upbringing are interdependent, integral, connected and dialectical in nature, and are the basis of forming the spiritual-ethical maturity of a person. Spiritual and moral education is the process of forming spiritual and moral consciousness, providing students with systematic knowledge about the essence of spiritual and moral relations, and creating the need to acquire spiritual and moral knowledge in them. lib, should be organized in a consistent, continuous, systematic way.

Organization of spiritual and moral education of students is a holistic pedagogical process directed towards specific goals. In this process, the following pedagogical tasks are solved:

1. Students will be informed about the nature of moral and ethical norms and moral relations and their importance in the life of the social society.
2. To create the need to acquire spiritual and moral knowledge in students, to establish spiritual and moral consciousness.
3. To establish positive spiritual and moral qualities in students (knowledge, diligence, humility, love, love for the country, people, respect for parents and elders, humanitarianism, generosity, devotion to duty, etc.).
4. Formation of behavior, character and will of the students in spiritual and moral content.
5. Forming the spiritual and moral culture of students.

Summary.

The determination of aesthetic and moral qualities can be seen in the historical-objective conditions of the individual's positive, moderate influence on the development of society, the improvement of human interaction, and the expansion of communication circles. The determination of spiritual and moral qualities takes place on the basis of the following general content:

- the student's spiritual and moral level is manifested in the process of social relations, in his approach to society, environment and nature;
- the student's spiritual and moral level depends on the level of social and spiritual development of the society;
- the spiritual and moral maturity of students is created as a result of the establishment of continuous, systematic education and training organized on the basis of mutual harmony of objective and subjective conditions;
- the spiritual and moral maturity of the student leads to positive results in establishing social relations.

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